

A STUDY ON JOB PERFORMANCE AND APPRAISAL OF EMPLOYEES IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SECTOR IN CHENNAI

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ABSTRACT

Job Performance is the measure of how a person performs a job and the expectations from him from the employer. Job performance of an employee is of significant value to all organizations as the success of business rests mainly on the employees making it imperative that they deliver a strong job performance. Job performance requires a clear understanding of one's goals and objectives, work ethics, effective communication, healthy relationship among co-workers and also good follow up from the employer, where Job appraisal plays a integral part. Job appraisal is a process of systematic evaluation of the job performance of an employee with an eye on scope of productivity, mutual growth and development of employee and employer. The IT industry is a booming business sector which comprises of software development, consultancies, software management, online services, business process outsourcing (BPO) and anything that deals with transmission of information. The IT industry is drastically changing the vision of Indian business community and has made India a great economic hub for economies of the world. Employees throng to the IT industry as it enables them a high standard of life with good earning potential and benefits of travelling across the globe. People prefer profession in IT sectors because they want to use their skills and capabilities. Improved Job performance is a key factor for all employees as there is high competition and all companies play major emphasis on Job appraisal as the industry is highly vibrant and dynamic .Most IT companies have started recognizing the effect of job performance and job appraisal and are increasing their focus on HR issues and employee motivational activities.

KEYWORDS: Job Performance, Job Appraisal, Information Technology, Productivity, Revenue, Motivational Factors.

INTRODUCTION

Job performance is the main factor for every employee to work for their organization and to update their intellectual and it develops the employee's interest for their growth and appraisal for their work of individual. In this busy world, every industry is growing with their resources and new technology has been improved and to show their keen interest to reach to all levels. Productivity improvement is the main criteria for business profitability and enhancement in the current scenario of competitiveness. To enhance job performance standards, effective employee performance management system is imperative for a business organization. In retrospect, there has been mentioning of satisfaction with performance appraisal and it has been referred to as one of the factors that increase the effectiveness of performance management systems. To achieve their goal each and every person has to develop their interest towards performing their job to a high level. In this study IT sector employees have to complete their targets on time and to achieve monthly basis target also show their outstanding performance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the factors influencing job performance in IT industries in Chennai.
- To study the various employee factors affecting job performance and job appraisal effect on different experience groups of employees.
- To provide suggestions for improvement of job performance and appraisal among all levels of employees.

Sources of Data

The survey was collected from two sources of data viz.,

1. Primary data
2. Secondary data

The data which has been collected through a Questionnaire is called Primary data. Data have been collected from 90 respondents. The secondary data has been taken through, Magazines, News Papers, books, Journals, Websites and other already published data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION: Table 5.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S No	Demographic Factors	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	50	55.56
		Female	40	44.44
2	Qualification	Professional	20	22.22
		Degree Holder	36	40.00
		Post Graduate	22	24.44
		Diploma Holder	12	13.33
3	Age Group	21-30 Years	23	25.56
		31-40 Years	34	37.78
		41-50 Years	18	20.00
		Above 50 Years	15	16.66
4	Experience Level	Less than 6 months	14	15.36
		6 months – 2 years	25	27.78
		2 – 5 Yrs	36	40
		More than 5 years	15	16.67
5	Income Group	Up to Rs.20,000	27	30.00
		Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000	16	17.78
		Rs.30,001 to 40,000	35	38.89
		Above Rs.40,000	12	13.33

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. Majority of respondents 55.56 percent of male and 44.44 percent of female respondents are participated in the survey. While taking educational qualification, 22.22 percent of respondents are Professional, 40 percent are degree holder, 24.44 percent are Professional degree holders and only a 13.33 percent are Diploma holders. From the above table 37.78 percent are in age group of 31-40 years, 25.56 percent of respondents are between 21-30 years, 20 percent of respondents between 41-50 years and 16.67 percent of respondents are more than 50 years. To know the income level, 30 percent of respondents come under income group up to Rs.20000, 17.78 percent of respondents between Rs.20000-30000, 38.89 percent of respondents between Rs.30000-40000 and 12 percent of respondents above Rs.40000. Majority of respondents 40 percent of employees are having experience of 2 -5 years, 27.78 percent of respondents are having experience of 6 months to 2 years, 16.67 percent of respondents have experience for more than 5 years while 15.36 percent are having less than 6 months of experience level.

Table 5.2 Factors influencing job performance

Sl. No.	Prominent features	Experience group			Total	χ^2
		Low	Middle	High		
1	Work Environment	3.78	3.33	3.18	3.46	.804
2	Collective Teamwork	2.36	3.11	3.55	3.08	.132
3	Advancement in Technology	3.48	3.30	3.01	3.32	.825
4	Organisation Commitment	3.05	2.93	3.23	3.06	.452
5	Training Methodology	3.10	2.83	3.15	3.01	.356

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table explains that factors influencing job performance. Work environment is the most prominent feature for IT employees among all experience groups with an overall mean of 3.46. In case of collective teamwork high experience group employees have rated 3.55. Advancement of technology secured 3.30 across middle experience group. Work environment and advancement of technology are high among middle experience groups as factors influencing job performance for employees of IT sector with mean value of 3.30. Work environment have scored high among low experience groups with a mean score of 3.46.

H₀1: There is no relationship between different experience group and factors influencing job performance.

The above hypothesis has been tested in the chi square test. The results are given in table no.4.29. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of work environment, collective teamwork, advancement in technology. In case of organization commitment and training methodology the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus it is concluded that there is a significant difference among experience group people on the factors influencing job performance from work environment, collective teamwork

Table 5.3 Factors affecting job performance and appraisal

Sl No	Aspects	Experience Level			Mean score	F-Statistics
		Low	Middle	High		
1	Appraisal methodology	3.12	3.46	3.01	3.19	.398

2	Performance monitoring	3.52	3.25	3.11	3.25	.009
3	Relationship with superiors	3.42	3.40	3.23	3.40	.429
4	Monetary and Non-Monetary Benefits	3.18	3.03	3.27	3.14	.699
5	Skill Set development	3.44	3.22	3.38	3.40	.579

Source: Computed Primary Data

Table 5.3 explains that factors affecting job performance and appraisal in IT sector by the various experience group people. From the less experience group Performance monitoring has scored the mean value of 3.52. In the middle experience group appraisal methodology has scored with a mean score of 3.46. Among high experience group Skill Set development has got highest mean score of 3.40. It is concluded that relationship with superiors and Skill Set development has provided high score 3.40 in case of employee factors affecting job performance and appraisal among all experience groups.

H₀₂: There is no significance between experience group and factors affecting job performance and appraisal.

The above hypothesis has been tested in the light one way ANOVA. The results are given in table no.5.3. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of appraisal methodology and Performance monitoring. In the case of Relationship with superiors the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus there is a significant difference among experience group people on the provision of training, teamwork and employee participation.

Findings

- 55.56 percent of respondents are male.
- 40 percent of respondents are degree holders
- 37.78 percent of employees are in age group of 31-40 yrs.
- 40 percent of employees are having experience for 2 - 5 yrs.
- 38.89 percent of employees are come under income group of Rs.30000 to Rs.40000.
- By Chi-square test there is no significant difference among different experience group and factors influencing for job performance
- Using F-Test, there is no relationship between different experience group and employee factors affecting job appraisal.

Suggestions

- Work Environment is the most prominent feature for all IT employees among all experience groups.
- There is a significant difference among experience group people on the factors influencing job performance technology for better performance from work environment, collective teamwork, advancement in technology
- There is a significant difference among experience group people on the appraisal methodology and Performance monitoring.
- Monetary and Non-Monetary benefits have to be focused for the improvement in job appraisal.

Conclusions

In the growing technology, IT companies play a significant role in the economy. In day to day each and every employee has learning new methods and technology for their job performance. Some of the factors have to be improved upon for better performance in job through collective teamwork and training methodology. Therefore to have appraisal in job performance monetary and non-monetary benefits has to be raised in order to have consistent in job performance. Suggestions to be made to IT companies for better job performance and appraisal can be achieved through of Work environment, advancement of technology, appraisal methodology and Performance monitoring and to have a cordial relationship among employees.

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